

IDEOLOGICAL PLURALISM IN UZBEKISTAN AND IT'S IMPACT ON STABILITY

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Annotation: *In today's globalization process, maintaining political and social stability is a very important task. This article analyzes the concept of ideological pluralism and the role and function of ideological pluralism in the implementation of the above tasks.*

Keywords: *Politics, ideological pluralism, society, concept, science, economic freedom.*

INTRODUCTION

Civil society is a complex and pluralistic system. Naturally, any social organism has a certain set of properties of the system, but civil society is characterized by their completeness, stability and efficiency. The existence of diverse social forms and institutions (trade unions, parties, associations, entrepreneurs, clubs, etc.) allows individuals to express and realize the needs and interests of different districts, to demonstrate all the abilities of mankind¹.

Ideological pluralism (Latin pluralism - diversity, diversity)² - a concept that expresses the ideological diversity, diversity of views and opinions, representing the interests of different strata, parties, groups in socio-political life. The more advanced ideas and ideologies in the country, that is, the more ideological pluralism prevails, the wider the opportunity to choose an effective path of development. The intellectual struggle serves to enrich the ideologies in terms of meaning and content, to complement each other. Ideological pluralism creates conditions for the emergence of new ideas that serve social development, the common realization of the interests of different peoples, ethnic groups, nations and political groups. It inevitably requires a multiparty system. Political parties, on the other hand, express the interests, aspirations, and aspirations of the strata to which they belong, through their programs of action.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

¹ Otamurodov S., Mamashokirov S., Kholbekov A. Central Asia: ideological processes and ideological threats.- T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2011.

² National Idea: Dictionary of Propaganda Technologies and Terms - T.: Akademiya, 2017. - pages 184, 220, 222. (National ideology: advocacy technologies and glossary of terms - T.: Academy, 2007. - pages 184, 220, 222)

Like all sciences, civil society science has its own laws and concepts. The universally recognized laws on the formation and development of civil society can be divided into 2 groups³.

1- group. Universal laws on the formation and development of civil society.

- decision and development of property relations;
- real and practical protection of human rights and freedoms;
- decentralization of public administration;
- The priority of the development of society on the basis of pluralistic ideas;
- Increasing the influence and position of citizens in decision-making on public administration;

-increasing the role of civil society institutions in public life;

-increasing impact of civic and civic activism on public life, etc.

2- group. Legislation that takes into account the specific aspects of the national and historical development of each country.

-formation of the middle class;

-increasing role and place of self-government institutions in public administration;

- Targeted organization and implementation of social protection;

-increasing the opportunities for spiritual maturity and the transformation of youth into a creative force, etc.

While the main element of civil society is the individual, civil society institutions, organizations, groups, etc. are the factors that shape it. They help to realize an individual's interests, goals, intentions, and other needs. Therefore, the separation of economic and political power is a key factor in the emergence and decision-making of a real civil society. When economic power is combined with political power, inevitably there is a concentration of economic power in the hands of one center, one person or group of individuals. If political and economic powers are concentrated in different centers, in different hands, they will limit each other.

Civil society security (public safety) is characterized by the following indicators:

-social justice;

-recognition of the rights of citizens and society as a whole in relations with the state;

- the order of legality;

- economic well-being of citizens;

- democratic pluralism;

³ Ochildiev A. National idea and interethnic relations.-T .: Uzbekistan, 2014.

- openness of society;
- The form of civil society is national, the content is universal.

The distinction between human rights and civil rights has certain grounds, which include⁴:

1) human rights can be recognized by the state and strengthened by law, regardless of whether the owner is a person or not. Civil rights are protected by the state to which the person belongs;

2) Many people in the world still do not have citizenship at all (stateless persons - apatrids). Consequently, they have official human rights, not civil rights. The task of civil society is to ensure the development of social life. Therefore, among the tasks of its main components are the activities of institutions that create the conditions for the normal course of this process.

The main features of civil society are:

- Association of Free Individuals;
- social structure based on mutual cooperation;
- pluricultural system with a complex structure;
- existence of self-developing and self-governing non-governmental structures.

The most important factors of civil society:

- 1) economic freedom, diversity of forms of ownership, market relations;
- 2) unconditional recognition and protection of the natural rights of man and citizen;
- 3) legitimacy and democratic nature of government;
- 4) equality of all before the law and justice, reliable legal protection of each person;
- 5) the rule of law based on the principle of separation of powers into three and the interaction of powers;
- 6) political and ideological pluralism, the existence of a constructive opposition;
- 7) freedom of speech and press, independence of the media;
- 8) non-interference of the state in the private life of citizens, their mutual obligations and duties;
- 9) class and national harmony, social partnership;
- 10) effective social policy that ensures a decent standard of living for people.

In the economic sphere, the basis of civil society is a multi-sectoral economy, various forms of property and managed market relations; In the legal sphere, the

⁴ Musaev F. Philosophical and legal bases of building a democratic state. -T.: Uzbekistan, 2017. -P.255

powers of government are not concentrated in the center, the separation of powers, political pluralism, participation of citizens in state and public affairs, the rule of law, equality before all; in the spiritual realm - the absence of a single ideology and monopoly of worldview, freedom of conscience, culture, high spirituality and morality.

Article 60 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Public Associations" states: "Political parties represent the political will of various classes and groups, and the state through their democratically elected representatives Political parties shall report publicly to the Oliy Majlis or the body it represents on the sources of funding for their activities in accordance with the established procedure⁵. This article of the Constitution stipulates that the ideological activity of political parties is under the control of the whole nation and is in full compliance with the principles of democracy.

Any society has a certain social structure, which includes different social strata, classes, groups, social institutions. The diversity of the social structure is the basis for the diversity of interests and aspirations of its constituent elements. Ideological views are a specific expression of these interests and aspirations, and become a system of logically based views that reflect the goals and activities of various forces. Accordingly, in any country, when creative ideas and ideological activity take precedence, the opportunities for national development expand. In the so-called "planet Earth" socio-political space: legal equality, freedom of will, peace will be established at the international level, friendly interethnic and interreligious relations will be strengthened⁶.

The idea of national development is to mobilize its potential to ensure the prospects of a particular state, taking into account the laws of objective development of society, the role of subjective factors in their implementation, specific historical conditions. In other words, the ideological and ideological reconciliation of domestic socio-political forces is a key condition for sustainable national development.

Changes in the life of Uzbekistan require great changes in the minds of people. In the period of transition, it is natural that any state is seriously concerned about the upbringing of a new generation. This means that in Uzbekistan, too, the task of determining the appropriate qualities of a person recognized in the idea of "perfect man" is facing citizens. Such education of "civic morality" is the basis of ideological policy.

⁵ The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan

⁶ O. Bozorov "National idea and effectiveness of propaganda". T.: "Ma" naviyat" 2018. B-20.

In Uzbekistan, the tasks of educating the younger generation to new thinking and thinking, to direct their political activity, to be faithful to the ideas of independence are being gradually implemented. In the process of globalization, a complete change in political and psychological guidelines demonstrates the urgency of ensuring information security for young people.

Structures of perception and struggle against danger are formed in the process of self-awareness. Analytical and critical thinking emerges in young people only after the formation of personal opinion, reflection, worldview.

The concept of movement is formed in the ability of young people to independently and correctly formulate their political concept, to clearly understand and analyze political processes, to understand its essence⁷.

At present, the organization of security on the basis of technological and technocratic methods is a requirement of the times. The task of ensuring information security of young people, in turn, requires the systematization of the process, the early guarantee of results, the ability to make adjustments to the process at any time.

The formation of information and psychological immunity of young people requires the following organizational work, such as systematization of the process on the basis of technology, which in turn reduces, generalizes and coordinates a number of tasks:

- Understanding the essence of existing political processes, their use in the formation of immunity;
- Analysis of the impact on youth decision-making;
- Developing the skills of young people to self-correct their decisions;
- Formation of youth self-monitoring and analysis.

It is also necessary to fully develop the political, socio-economic and psychological factors that affect young people. This should allow to eliminate the shortcomings in a timely manner.

CONCLUSION

The next stage of propaganda requires a correct and comprehensive explanation of the idea, finding answers to all questions related to ideology. Because to understand the national idea is to believe in it. Here we are faced with the question: what is more convincing: information based on solid evidence or an emotional speech? Of course, it is very effective to appeal to the feelings and heart

⁷ Tashmetov, T. X. (2021). Mechanisms to increase the effectiveness of the national idea in the use of global achievements. Academic research in educational science, 2 (3), 596-602.

of a person during the propaganda. But objectivity, credible evidence, non-objectionable factual information give the impression that we are all interested in putting these ideas into practice.

Those who think that the propaganda process ends here are making a big mistake. After all, ideology inspires new things, motivates action. Inactive ideology is nothing but nonsense. This means that only when people begin to act in accordance with the ideas of the national ideology can we conclude that the national idea has become the belief of the people.

Ensuring that it is tailored to the specific audience is the most important factor in ensuring the effectiveness of the campaign.

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